

Advancing Geospatial Data Integration: The Role of Prompt Engineering in Semantic Association with chatGPT

Fabiola Andrade Souza^{1,2}, Silvana Philippi Camboim²

¹ Polytechnic School, Federal University of Bahia, Salvador-BA, Brazil – fabiola.andrade@ufba.br

² Dept. of Geomatics, Federal University of Paraná, Curitiba-PR, Brazil – silvanacamboim@ufpr.br

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Abstract

Semantic interoperability is essential for integrating open geospatial collaborative and official data. While geosemantics has long been a topic of discussion, recent research has explored automated semantic integration without fully leveraging the capabilities of large language models (LLMs) in artificial intelligence. This study investigates using chatGPT-4 to semantically associate OpenStreetMap (OSM) tags with the Brazilian topographic mapping model, the Technical Specification for Structuring Vector Geospatial Data (ET-EDGV). Focusing on five classes within the buildings category, the study tested three data structuring methods: spreadsheets, OWL ontology, and XML. Results indicated that ontology and XML formats produced more accurate semantic associations than spreadsheets, with OWL yielding the most coherent results. These findings underscore the importance of properly structured data to capture hierarchical relationships between concepts better. The study also noted the need for precise and detailed queries, highlighting some limitations in chatGPT's ability to understand complex geospatial model inputs. Further research is recommended to enhance LLMs' potential in facilitating semantic interoperability and to explore the role of prompt engineering in optimizing these interactions.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, semantic web technologies have enabled users to transition from passive consumers to active participants, directly interacting with data and becoming information producers, particularly in geospatial data. This type of data, which serves as the basis for map creation, is often influenced by the user or producer's local perceptions and social contexts. This relationship broadens the scope of territorial analysis by integrating local perspectives into a global context (Fernandes *et al.*, 2020; Machado and Camboim, 2024).

A notable example is the collaborative mapping platform OpenStreetMap (OSM), where users generate data through individual and collective efforts, such as disaster relief initiatives led by the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT). In their data production, users select a tag (key+value pair) from the platform to identify the object to be represented, or they create tags if the existing ones are inadequate for what they wish to represent. Initially mirrored in the definition of objects represented within the European context, this model grants its community a certain degree of freedom in semantic definitions. However, this flexibility presents challenges in integrating with other geospatial data models (OSM, 2024; Machado and Camboim, 2024).

Studies indicate that integrating collaborative data with official data offers mutual benefits (Anand *et al.*, 2010; Fernandes *et al.*, 2020). Achieving this integration requires interoperability between databases, emphasizing the importance of understanding the semantics of each model. In cartography, the representation of objects on a map begins with defining the features to be depicted, a process shaped by the sociocultural contexts of users or producers (MacEachren, 1994; Sluter *et al.*, 2019).

Geosemantic discussions are not new and highlight the critical role of database integration through the conceptual understanding of objects (Kuhn, 2003). However, it is only in recent years that research has focused on automated semantic integration for distinct data schemas (Anand *et al.*, 2010; Ballatore *et al.*, 2013; Machado and Camboim, 2024), and even then, the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in this process remains largely unexplored.

The use of AI in the geospatial field has expanded significantly in recent decades, particularly with applications of machine learning and deep learning for remote sensing and photogrammetry studies (Chamma *et al.*, 2021). Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools, which handle tasks such as text analysis, categorization, generation, and manipulation, have gained attention in various fields. However, their application in geospatial modelling remains underexplored.

NLP applies linguistic modelling techniques to a prior knowledge base by learning the probability distribution over sequences of symbols in a language, performing syntactic and semantic interpretation of the text – known as perplexity measurement (Jozefowicz *et al.*, 2016). For this purpose, it utilizes neural networks based on mathematical models, with generative networks based on the Transformer architecture recently gaining prominence. These networks have enabled large language models (LLMs) to feed these networks with datasets comprising billions of parameters (Vaswani *et al.*, 2017).

However, it is important to note that even with the recent advancements in applying LLMs to NLP, the tools still present some limitations, particularly in the geographic context, especially when addressing spatial analyses or topological operations that require deeper analytical insight (Meng *et al.*, 2024; Zhang *et al.*, 2024b). Geospatial data is part of a specific knowledge domain with diverse structures and sources, including images, vectors, and text, which pose significant challenges to its effective use (Mooney *et al.*, 2023). The semantics of this type of data extend beyond textual concerns, encompassing the spatial relationships between the represented objects.

Among the LLMs currently in use are BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers), GPT (Generative Pre-Trained Transformer), and T5 (Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer), which can be applied in the development of specific tools, such as chatGPT, which uses the GPT model in various versions, or Google Bard, which utilizes BERT. These LLMs can also be used to develop non-proprietary specific tools, as some programming languages offer libraries to work with them, such as the Transformers package in Python.

These LLM-based tools have shown a promising future, enabling human-like dialogues, although they still depend on the quality

of the training dataset and the execution of dialogue prompts for interaction (Zhang *et al.*, 2024). This has led to the emergence of prompt engineering, a field that focuses on developing effective strategies for human-machine communication within NLP.

Through prompt engineering, the user can communicate with the tools through a dialogue box (prompt) using short and simple text without examples (zero-shot) or with texts that present one or more contextualization examples (one-shot or few-shot), aiming to facilitate machine learning during the communication process and improve the responses (Dang *et al.*, 2022; Wang *et al.*, 2023). It is argued that LLMs are few-shot learners, meaning they can learn new tasks with only a few examples. In practice, however, their performance has remained inconsistent, and "it is unclear to what extent they are extrapolating from learned examples rather than simply interpolating or literally copying" (Prince, 2023, p. 225).

Nevertheless, preliminary studies by Souza and Camboim (2023) demonstrated the feasibility of using chatGPT for the semantic association between OSM data and the Technical Specification for Structuring Vector Geospatial Data (ET-EDGV), the conceptual data modelling for Brazilian topographic mapping. This study communicated through a direct dialogue prompt in sequential text, organizing the object concepts of each model. However, the authors highlight gaps regarding how to interact with an LLM.

Although the most common method of interaction with large language models (LLMs) is through sequential text, where the model architecture calculates the distance between terms previously fragmented into tokens, it is crucial to explore alternative input formats. In this case, we are investigating prompts that provide LLMs with structured data formats to facilitate the model's understanding of hierarchical or spatial relationships. Conceptual data models, particularly geospatial ones, incorporate complex representation and knowledge hierarchy elements, including geometries and spatial relationships, as Machado and Camboim (2024) mentioned when comparing the taxonomic structures of OSM and ET-EDGV.

Given ongoing discussions around prompt engineering, it is essential to investigate its potential in the context of geospatial data. Therefore, this study aims to explore different interaction methods with chatGPT-4 to identify communication strategies suitable for enabling the semantic association of objects in conceptual geospatial data models, using OSM and ET-EDGV as case studies.

2. Materials and Methods

The methodology applied in this study first consisted of evaluating the proposed data schemas (ET-EDGV and OSM – sections 2.1 and 2.2) and selecting a representative set of object concepts to be explored. Thus, the hierarchical structure of ET-EDGV was used as the main reference, and five classes from the "Buildings" category were selected: Generic Building, Commerce and Service, Health, Education, and Fuel Station.

The OSM tags were then semantically associated with the classes using chatGPT, consulting the concepts listed on the platform's official website (OSM, 2024).

The conceptual data of the selected classes from ET-EDGV were reorganized according to different knowledge organization formats proposed for interaction with the tool, including a spreadsheet, ontology, and model converted to Extensible Markup Language (XML), as detailed in section 2.3.

Finally, a dialogue was conducted with chatGPT for each format, requesting the most appropriate semantically associated tags for each presented class (section 2.4). The results were organized into tables and graphs and analyzed.

2.1 ET-EDGV Conceptual Model

The Technical Specification for Structuring Vector Geospatial Data – ET-EDGV (Concar, 2017) is the conceptual model for vector geospatial data used to produce the official reference databases in Brazil within the context of the National Spatial Data Infrastructure – INDE.

ET-EDGV applies the object-oriented model, Object Modeling Technique for Geographic Applications – OMT-G, representing geospatial objects of interest to cartography and their topological relationships (Borges *et al.*, 2005). Its hierarchical structure presents different taxonomic levels, as described by Machado and Camboim (2024), which include scale, category, class (for objects), and their attributes (with specific domains and data types, including geometries).

Nineteen categories are presented: energy and communications, economic structure, hydrography, boundaries and localities, landmarks, relief, sanitation, transportation systems (general, airport, pipeline, rail, waterway, and road), and vegetation. Additionally, categories such as green areas, base classes, culture and leisure, buildings, and urban mobility are also addressed.

The buildings category includes 34 geospatial classes and two conventional classes. The 'Building' class, the most generic, represents any type of construction, while the remaining subclasses are specialized based on the specific usage of buildings. This category was selected for this study due to its relevance in urban mapping (Fernandes *et al.*, 2020) and the substantial volume of data it presents in OSM. However, future research can extend methodology to other classes and categories. This study focused on a subset of five classes from the buildings category for analysis: Building, Commerce and Service, Health, Education, and Fuel Station. Only the attribute defining its usage typology, when applicable, and the corresponding domains were considered for each class, as shown in Table 1.

Class	Domain
Building	No typology attribute
Commercial or Service Building	Newsstand
Commercial or Service Building	Bank
Commercial or Service Building	Meat Shop
Commercial or Service Building	Shopping Center
Commercial or Service Building	Convention Center
Commercial or Service Building	Exhibition Center
Commercial or Service Building	Pharmacy
Commercial or Service Building	Hotel
Commercial or Service Building	Convenience Store
Commercial or Service Building	Building Materials and/or Hardware Store
Commercial or Service Building	Furniture Store
Commercial or Service Building	Clothing and/or Fabric Store
Commercial or Service Building	Public Market
Commercial or Service Building	Motel
Commercial or Service Building	Auto Repair Shop
Commercial or Service Building	Inn
Commercial or Service Building	Kiosk
Commercial or Service Building	Greengrocer
Commercial or Service Building	Restaurant
Commercial or Service Building	Supermarket
Commercial or Service Building	Vehicle Dealership
Education Building	No typology attribute
Health Building	Primary
Health Building	Secondary
Health Building	Tertiary
Fuel Station	No typology attribute

Table 1. Hierarchical Structure of ET-EDGV Used.

2.2 OSM Conceptual Model

OpenStreetMap (OSM) is the most relevant platform for producing collaborative geospatial data within discussions on Volunteered Geographic Information (VGI). Its community creates and maintains an open database that can be edited by any participant, aiming to represent spatial and sociocultural elements from anywhere in the world (Fernandes *et al.*, 2020; OSM, 2024).

Unlike ET-EDGV, its taxonomic structure presents other hierarchical elements. The first level concerns the language used, followed by the tag, composed of a key + value pair to identify a geospatial object. Lastly, there is the geometric representation element, suggestions for symbology, and sample images of a real object. This structure, as presented by Machado and Camboim (2024), is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Taxonomic Structure of OpenStreetMap. Source: Machado and Camboim (2024).

2.3 Geodata Format

The different knowledge organization formats proposed for interaction with chatGPT were applied to the conceptual hierarchy of ET-EDGV in the five selected classes and their respective domains¹, which are as follows:

- (i) a spreadsheet with columns indicating class, attribute, domain, and their respective concepts – figure 2;
- (ii) an ontology in the Ontology Web Language (OWL) format, created using the free software Protégé version 4.5 – figure 3;
- (iii) an Extensible Markup Language (XML) file exported from the Object Modeling Technique for Geographic (OMT-G) modelling, generated through the free tool OMT-G Designer² – figures 4 and 5.

CLASS	CLASS DEFINITION	ATRIBUTE	ATRIBUTE DEFINITION	DOMAIN
Edificação	Edificação é uma construção destinada a diversos fins.			
Edificação de ensino	Edificação de ensino é aquela cujas atividades estão relacionadas à formação e/ou aperfeiçoamento e/ou pesquisa de cunho educacional.			
Edificação de saúde	Edificação de saúde é aquela cujas atividades estão relacionadas ao atendimento médico e/ou pesquisa no campo de saúde.	nívelAtencao	Indica o nível de atenção à saúde. Abrange os postos ou centros de saúde.	Primário
Edificação de saúde	Edificação de saúde é aquela cujas atividades estão relacionadas ao atendimento médico e/ou pesquisa no campo de saúde.	nívelAtencao	Indica o nível de atenção à saúde. Abrange os hospitais gerais.	Secundário
Edificação de saúde	Edificação de saúde é aquela cujas atividades estão relacionadas ao atendimento médico e/ou pesquisa no campo de saúde.	nívelAtencao	Indica o nível de atenção à saúde. Abrange os hospitais especializados.	Terciário
Posto de combustível	Posto de combustível é o local onde são feitos os abastecimentos de combustíveis aos veículos e embarcações que trafegam por uma via de transporte.			
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Edificação de comércio ou serviços é uma edificação com funcionalidades comerciais ou de prestação de serviços.	tipoEdifComercS	Indica o tipo da edificação comercial ou de serviços.	Banca de jornal
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Edificação de comércio ou serviços é uma edificação com funcionalidades comerciais ou de prestação de serviços.	tipoEdifComercS	Indica o tipo da edificação comercial ou de serviços.	Banco
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Edificação de comércio ou serviços é uma edificação com funcionalidades comerciais ou de prestação de serviços.	tipoEdifComercS	Indica o tipo da edificação comercial ou de serviços.	Comércio de carnes

Figure 2. Hierarchical Structure of ET-EDGV Classes - Spreadsheet.

Figure 3. Hierarchical Structure of ET-EDGV Classes - OWL.

Figure 4. Hierarchical Structure ET-EDGV Classes - OMT-G.

¹ Examples in Portuguese – ET-EDGV language.

² <http://aqui.io/omt/>

```

▼ <class>
  <name>Edif_Saude</name>
  <top>430</top>
  <left>830</left>
  <type>polygon</type>
  ▼ <attributes>
    ▼ <attribute>
      <name>nivelAtencao</name>
      <type>TEXT</type>
    </attribute>
  </attributes>
</class>
▶ <class>
  ...
</class>
▶ <class>
  ...
</class>
▼ <class>
  <name>nivelAtencao</name>
  <top>596</top>
  <left>835</left>
  <type>conventional</type>
  ▼ <attributes>
    ▼ <attribute>
      <name>Primário</name>
      <type>TEXT</type>
    </attribute>
    ▼ <attribute>
      <name>Secundário</name>
      <type>TEXT</type>
    </attribute>
  </attributes>
  ▼ <attribute>
    <name>Terciário</name>
    <type>TEXT</type>
  </attribute>
</attributes>
</class>

```

Figure 5. Hierarchical Structure ET-EDGV Classes - XML.

2.4 Interaction with chatGPT

Finally, for each of the three formats of structuring the conceptual hierarchy of ET-EDGV, chatGPT was asked about the OSM tags that would be most suitable for semantic association with the classes. Figure 6 presents an example of the query using the ontology structure. For the other hierarchical structures of the model, the same question was used, adjusting the text when it referred to the data format.

Considering the classes and subclasses of the ET-EDGV read from the OWL, as well as the conceptual modeling of geospatial data from OpenStreetMap (OSM), presented at the link https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Map_Features, with the identification of their tags composed of a key and a value, in addition to the respective concepts.

1- Indicate, in order of highest probability, the most appropriate OSM tags (key+value) for semantic association with the classes and subclasses of the informed ontology.
2- Present the result in an XLSX spreadsheet, with columns indicating the name of the class or subclass and the names of the key and value of each associated tag.

Figure 6. Example of a question posed to chatGPT.

The responses generated by chatGPT, in the form of sequential text within the dialogue prompt, indicated the tag associated with each class or domain and were exported by the tool into a spreadsheet, as requested. These responses were later organized into a single table and a graph to facilitate the visualization of relationships.

While it is true that chatGPT-4, the LLM-based tool used in this study, is neither open-source nor freely available, the essence of this research lies in exploring the structure of communication with large language models and the hierarchical organization of geospatial concepts. This goes beyond the constraints of a specific proprietary tool and delves into a broader methodological inquiry.

Crucially, the data structures we employed – such as spreadsheets, ontologies, and XML – are fully open, ensuring the methodology is transparent and reproducible. These open formats make it possible to replicate the process using other AI tools based on LLMs, including open-source options. The decision to use chatGPT was made to streamline the research process and prioritize the analysis of the dialogue prompt architecture rather than the tool itself. In this regard, our work remains closely aligned with the open philosophy, as it leverages open databases like OSM and ET-EDGV, fostering integration with open geospatial infrastructures.

3. Results and Discussions

The results provided by chatGPT were not identical for the different data input formats, although most of the semantic associations in the responses were consistent and similar across them. Figure 7 presents a table that identifies the ET-EDGV class and the domains of its usage typology, associated with the key + value pair corresponding to the tag suggested by chatGPT, according to the input format (spreadsheet, OWL, or XML). The material used for the analyses is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/fabiolandrade/prompt>.

ET-EDGV (in portuguese)		CHATGPT (SPREADSHEET)		CHATGPT (OWL)		CHATGPT (XML)	
CLASS	DOMAIN	KEY	VALUE	KEY	VALUE	KEY	VALUE
Edificação	-	building	yes	-	-	building	yes
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	-	-	-	amenity	commercial_service	buildinguse	commercial
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Banco de jornal	shop	newsagent	shop	newsagent	shop	newsagent
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Banco	amenity	bank	amenity	bank	amenity	bank
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Comércio de carnes	shop	butcher	shop	butcher	shop	butcher
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Centro comercial	shop	mall	shop	mall	shop	mall
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Centro de convenções	-	-	amenity	conference_centre	amenity	conference_centre
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Centro de exposições	-	-	amenity	exhibition_centre	amenity	exhibition_centre
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Farmácia	amenity	pharmacy	amenity	pharmacy	amenity	pharmacy
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Hotel	-	-	tourism	hotel	tourism	hotel
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Loja de conveniência	-	-	shop	convenience	shop	convenience
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Loja de material de construção e/ou ferragem	-	-	-	-	-	-
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Loja de móveis	-	-	shop	furniture	shop	furniture
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Loja de roupas e/ou tecidos	shop	clothes	-	-	shop	clothes
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Mercado público	-	-	amenity	marketplace	marketplace	market
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Motel	-	-	tourism	motel	amenity	motel
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Oficina mecânica	-	-	shop	car_repair	shop	car_repair
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Pousada	-	-	tourism	guest_house	tourism	guest_house
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Quiosque	-	-	amenity	fast_food	amenity	kiosk
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Quitanda	-	-	shop	greengrocer	shop	greengrocer
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Restaurante	amenity	restaurant	amenity	restaurant	amenity	restaurant
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Supermercado	shop	supermarket	shop	supermarket	shop	supermarket
Edificação de Comércio ou Serviço	Venda de veículos	-	-	shop	car	shop	car
Edificação de ensino	-	amenity	school	amenity	school_university	amenity	school
Edificação de saúde	-	-	-	amenity	healthcare	healthcare	clinic
Edificação de saúde	Primário	amenity	clinic	amenity	doctors	healthcare	primary
Edificação de saúde	Secundário	amenity	hospital	amenity	hospital	healthcare	secondary
Edificação de saúde	Terciário	amenity	hospital	amenity	clinic	healthcare	tertiary
Posto de combustível	-	amenity	fuel	amenity	fuel	amenity	fuel
Classe não indicada explicitamente	Café	amenity	cafe	-	-	-	-
Classe não indicada explicitamente	Universidade	amenity	university	-	-	-	-
Classe não indicada explicitamente	Escola	amenity	school	-	-	-	-
Classe não indicada explicitamente	Jardim de infância	amenity	kindergarten	-	-	-	-
Classe não indicada explicitamente	Centro de saúde	amenity	clinic	-	-	-	-
Classe não indicada explicitamente	Gasolina	fuel	gasoline	-	-	-	-
Classe não indicada explicitamente	Diesel	fuel	diesel	-	-	-	-
Classe não indicada explicitamente	GNV	fuel	ong	-	-	-	-

Figure 7. Semantic Association using chatGPT - table.

For example, it was observed that when the input was in XML format, a tag was returned for each class or domain, except for the domain "Building materials and/or hardware store" in the Commercial or Service Building class. In most of these responses, the results indicated either more general tags, such as building+yes for the building class, or more specific ones, like amenity+fuel for Fuel Station.

Similarly, almost all classes or domains received associations when the input was structured as an ontology in OWL format. The exceptions were the generic Building class and the domains

"Building materials and/or hardware store" and "Clothing and/or fabric store" within the Commercial or Service Building class, which had no associated tags.

In contrast, the input in spreadsheet format presented the fewest correct associations (14 tags for 29 classes/domains) and suggested eight tags associated with domains not explicitly present in the ET-EDGV, such as 'café', 'jardim de infância' or 'diesel', although thematically related to the types of buildings researched. In this case, there appeared to be less understanding of the hierarchical and conceptual context between objects, although the LLM demonstrated an understanding of individual elements' concepts.

The semantic associations returned by chatGPT, according to each data input format, can also be seen in the graph in Figure 8, which highlights the predominance of OSM tags with the key corresponding to amenity or shop, along with previous analyses from a different visual perspective.

Figure 8. Semantic Association using chatGPT - graph.

It was also noted that among the tags returned, nine were proposed across the three data input formats; eight appeared only with input in OWL, and eight only in XML; ten for the spreadsheet input, including eight that had no direct association with ET-EDGV; nine came from input in OWL and XML; two came from spreadsheet and XML, and only one came from input with spreadsheet and OWL. This shows that the entries in OWL and XML formats provided more coherent returns individually and in combination.

Although the largest number of tags was returned for the XML data input, this approach presented some conceptual inconsistencies in the associations. For instance, in the domains of the Health Building class, which feature levels of care such as primary, secondary, and tertiary, the tool associated the tags healthcare+primary, healthcare+secondary, and healthcare+tertiary, which are not appropriate to the original concept.

On the other hand, the results from using the OWL input in the healthcare domain yielded more accurate semantic associations, returning the tags amenity+doctors for primary care, amenity+hospital for secondary care, and amenity+clinic for

tertiary care, which aligned well with the intended concepts (see Figure 9). This outcome underscores the importance of properly structured input data, as the OWL format effectively conveyed the hierarchical relationships and semantics of the healthcare concepts, allowing the LLM to interpret the input more consistently and accurately.

Figure 9. Semantic Association using chatGPT - healthcare.

The superior performance of OWL, in this case, is likely due to its inherent structure, which explicitly defines relationships between concepts and their attributes. OWL helps the LLM discern the nuances between different care levels (primary, secondary, tertiary) more effectively than sequential text by providing clear ontological hierarchies. This performance suggests that structured data formats like OWL can enhance the LLM's capacity to process and interpret complex conceptual relationships, improving the model's overall performance in tasks requiring semantic precision.

However, this process also revealed certain limitations. One significant challenge was the need for prompts to be as direct and detailed as possible. Multiple iterations of questions were required to obtain a coherent and meaningful response from chatGPT. This iterative querying process, often yielding only partial answers, points to the tool's limitations in processing complex hierarchical inputs within the current environment. It suggests that while the potential for LLMs to facilitate semantic interoperability is promising, their reliance on dialogue-based, tokenized text processing introduces constraints.

These limitations highlight the necessity of further refinement in the tools used and the input structuring methods to use LLMs fully for geospatial applications. Addressing these constraints, such as improving the ability of LLMs to handle more complex hierarchical queries in a single prompt, will be key to unlocking their potential for more seamless semantic integration processes.

4. Final Considerations and Recommendations

This study aimed to explore different interaction methods with a large language model tool – chatGPT – to enable the semantic association of objects defined in distinct conceptual geospatial data models, such as OSM and ET-EDGV. The results showed that using an ontology structure in OWL format provided more suitable outcomes than other formats like spreadsheets and XML. Although fewer tags were returned from the OWL input

than XML, the semantic associations were more coherent and better aligned with the intended concepts.

The spreadsheet format, on the other hand, produced the least accurate results. Not only did it generate fewer tag suggestions, but it also included tags for concepts that were not explicitly defined in the ET-EDGV schema, suggesting a weaker understanding of the hierarchical structure. These findings suggest that structured data formats, particularly ontologies, facilitate more accurate communication with LLMs by making the hierarchical relationships between concepts more explicit.

However, this work also revealed the need for further research to improve both the process and the tools used. Future studies should consider structuring the entire data hierarchy as an ontology to provide a more comprehensive test of the LLM's capabilities. Expanding the range of classes associated with different thematic categories could also offer deeper insights into the model's performance. Another important avenue for exploration is the development of custom GPTs, specifically trained for semantic association tasks in open-source environments, which could offer greater control and adaptability for geospatial applications.

Additionally, optimizing the query process is crucial. Reducing the number of interactions required for coherent responses would improve both the quality and the response time of the LLM. Finally, it is recommended that future studies explore other LLMs and tools beyond chatGPT, particularly those with open-source frameworks, to assess their suitability for semantic interoperability in geospatial contexts.

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